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Title

DiSSCo Prepare WP3 – Milestone 3.9: Secondment Procedures for DiSSCo

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Abstract

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This report examines examples of secondment schemes and suggests an approach to secondment in the DiSSCo context – which should offer tangible benefits for DiSSCo, as well as normal secondment benefits to the individuals and institutions involved. Other options for skills sharing and collaborative working include distributed working, and this will be examined further in the future work of Task 3.3 of DiSSCo Prepare.

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Secondment Procedures for DiSSCo

DiSSCo Prepare WP3 – Milestone 3.9

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This report examines examples of secondment schemes and suggests an approach to secondment in the DiSSCo context – which should offer tangible benefits for DiSSCo, as well as normal secondment benefits to the individuals and institutions involved. Other options for skills sharing and collaborative working include distributed working, and this will be examined further in the future work of Task 3.3 of DiSSCo Prepare.

Key words

Secondment, human resources, digitisation,
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01 INTRODUCTION

As a distributed infrastructure, both the preparation and delivery of the Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo) depend on the skills and expertise of members and partners from many countries and institutions, each of whom have something distinct to contribute. As well as each individual having their own unique skills and experience, organisations may specialise in particular areas, whether that's in terms of taxonomy or technologies.

DiSSCo Prepare Task 3.3 focuses on secondment and distributed working practices, as part of the overall capacity enhancement and collaborative working required to achieve DiSSCo's aims. Capacity enhancement requires working together effectively in cross-institutional teams to deliver; sharing expertise; and transferring scarce knowledge and skills where possible. This Milestone focuses on secondment procedures for DiSSCo - where secondment includes various options for assignment of a member of staff from one team or organisation to another for a fixed period or project, with the expectation that they will return to their original role. This task was originally conceived before the global Covid 19 pandemic made virtual collaboration a daily necessity of working life for many; arguably, traditional secondment involving individuals going to physically work away from their main employing institution may now be less relevant - but we believe there are still circumstances where it offers opportunities and benefits. This report therefore looks at what secondment means - including in this new context; case studies of secondment schemes, policies and models; analysis of secondment procedures in relation to DiSSCo needs; and recommendations.

The challenge of scarce skills and expertise is perhaps most acute for DiSSCo in digital / technical, engineering and project management areas, where specialist staff are fundamental to delivering core parts of the DiSSCo Programme, but are perhaps less traditionally to be found in the natural history collections sector. These are also areas where there is high competition for skills across many sectors, some of which are able to offer salaries well in excess of those usually available in collections institutions. The Conceptual design blueprint for the DiSSCo Infrastructure¹ (para. 3.12.2.1) raises the question 'How to build a sense of team – of community endeavour and resilience – in a multinational, distributed engineering team?' It recognises the need for common goals, and for close collaboration with other staff, mentioning the possibility of buddies, co-design methods and secondment to help build this important collegiate approach to technical development.

This milestone draws on the work of DiSSCo Prepare Task 3.1² about the competencies required to underpin the DiSSCo infrastructure; and is complementary to DiSSCo Prepare Work Package 2 considerations about the DiSSCo training strategy and Human Resources policies.

¹ Hardisty A, Saarenmaa H, Casino A, Dillen M, Gödderz K, Groom Q, Hardy H, Koureas D, Nieva de la Hidalga A, Paul DL, Runnel V, Vermeersch X, van Walsum M, Willemse L (2020) Conceptual design blueprint for the DiSSCo digitization infrastructure - DELIVERABLE D8.1. Research Ideas and Outcomes 6: e54280. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.6.e54280>

² Hardy, H., Koivunen, A., Groom, Q., Mergen, P., Berger, F., von Mering, S., Giere, P., Figueira, R., Arsénio, P., & Cartaxana, A. (2021). DiSSCo Prepare Deliverable D3.1 "Summary Insights and Recommendations on DiSSCo Competencies and Digital Maturity". DiSSCo Prepare. <https://doi.org/10.34960/3pc3-pp32>

02 WHAT IS 'SECONDMENT'?

2.1 Meaning and aims

Secondment can be defined as 'the assignment of a member of one organisation to another organisation for a temporary period'³. It can also be used to refer to assignment across different teams within the same larger organisation - an internal secondment. A key feature is that a secondment is for a fixed term, and is outside the person's normal team and responsibilities (i.e. they do not undertake this alongside continuing their existing work). The aim of such an assignment typically includes exchange of knowledge and skills; liaison between the organisations; and in longer secondments delivery of defined pieces of work. It is also common for a secondment to offer some benefit to both of the teams or institutions involved as well as to the individual, although the benefits to each party may not be equivalent in type or value. For example, the receiving institution may benefit from work being done; the individual from gaining new skills; and the 'lending' institution from those skills being applied when the individual returns to their original role.

As mentioned above, the duration of a secondment can vary from days or weeks to a year or even sometimes more, although the most typical would perhaps be 3-12 months. In the DiSSCo context, secondments might range from short term placements where staff with specialist skills undertake learning or short projects with a host to deliver pre-agreed outcomes; through to longer-term staff transfers to deliver programme-level objectives in capacity improvement or technical delivery such as setting up institutional digital teams or implementing major pieces of DiSSCo technical infrastructure.

Traditionally a secondment would involve physical attendance to work with a different organisation (or a different team within an organisation) - however there is now a degree of overlap between secondment and other forms of distributed team working. It would be possible for a secondment agreement involving delivery of work, sharing of expertise etc to be agreed on a wholly or partly virtual basis, although this could impact the type of benefits expected. There is still a distinction between distributed working which would form part of an individual's normal role, and secondment where they are undertaking work outside their normal role for a fixed period (and therefore usually not undertaking most or all of their normal activities).

Secondment is also distinct from other forms of acquiring external expertise such as consultancy - the dynamic of a secondment is usually that of peer-to-peer or similar collaborative partnership or exchange, rather than a commercial payment for agreed services / value. It is possible that commercially based consultancy between organisations in DiSSCo may also occur in the context of delivering work and capability building, but this is not addressed in this paper.

2.2 How secondments work

Key considerations for organising secondments include:

- Salary level and employment rights of the individual on secondment (the default tending to be that the individual retains these from their primary organisation);
- Who is administering and paying the salary, taxes and other benefits or charges such as pension or social security - particularly in the case of longer term or international

³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Secondment> (page accessed 19/04/2022)

secondments. It is possible to have models in which, for instance, the salary level is determined by the primary organisation but the secondment host organisation or other body may administer payment for the duration of the secondment;

- Who meets any other costs such as overheads, travel and administration or management of individual secondments, and/or of a secondment scheme that may have multiple participants;
- The distribution of expected benefits - typically there would need to be benefit to both the primary and host organisations, and/or to DiSSCo in a wider sense, but as mentioned above these may not always be distributed equally;
- The incentives for organisations to participate in secondment, whether lending or receiving staff (which is linked to benefits and costs)

Section three below examines examples of secondment schemes and procedures in more detail.

03 CASE STUDIES OF SECONDMENT

3.1 The Natural History Museum, London (NHM)

The NHM has recently produced a policy for secondment and internal recruitment - the full text of this is at Annex 1. While this does not explicitly consider international secondment, it does address a variety of models of internal and external secondment (not all of which are currently in use at the NHM but which the policy wants to make provision for in future). The cases covered by this policy are:

- External secondment - either with the Museum remaining the employer or the host organisation taking over this responsibility for a fixed term;
- A formal secondment programme or scheme (run by the NHM);
- Informal internal secondment of less than 6 months (through placement not recruitment); or
- Formal internal secondment through recruitment of up to 18 months.

Any longer period than 18 months is treated as a full transfer to a new role.

The key features of this policy are to establish principles about, for example, the level to which open advertisement and recruitment is required in each set of circumstances, without defining the terms of particular secondment schemes. This is a similar approach to what is likely to be achievable currently with DiSSCo, prior to particular secondment scheme proposals or funding being discussed or available.

3.2 Examples of UK Publicly funded and academic secondment schemes

The Civil Service in the UK has a long history of secondment, interchange and loan of staff⁴, both between different teams or departments within the service and to external bodies such as private companies. Current policy is that where staff are seconded to an external organisation, the Civil Service continues to pay their salary. Where they move to another department, that host department becomes their employer and they are subject to relevant staff terms and conditions of that employer. Secondments are recognised to vary widely in their aims, terms etc and are treated individually - staff and managers are required to agree business cases for individual secondments and document secondment agreements including the responsibilities of all parties.

Undertaking secondments is usually for the reasons discussed above i.e. to develop and share skills, often through carrying out a specific piece of work, and always for a fixed time period. One issue that can arise in longer term secondments is that reward and promotion by the host department is not then recognised on return to the original employer - it is sensible to consider this explicitly in any secondment policy to manage expectations.

The UK also funds opportunities for collaboration and co-working between the public, private and academic sectors. An example of this is the Knowledge Transfer Partnership/Network schemes⁵. These are not traditional secondment schemes and have a focus on innovation, for example to help research move towards industrial applications or to help industry or government find relevant

⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/civil-service-secondments-and-loans-how-to-apply> (page accessed 19/04/2022)

⁵ https://ktn-uk.org/opportunities/?_sft_type_of_funding=knowledge-transfer-partnership (page accessed 19/04/2022)

researchers who can help them to resolve problems. The scheme refers to bringing together ‘business partners’ with ‘knowledgebase partners’, although in practice quite a wide range of working arrangements are possible. While these are not secondment schemes exactly, their focus on specific, strategic and demonstrable innovation outcomes is useful and worth considering in a DiSSCo context.

The Open University in the UK publishes their policies for staff secondment⁶. This policy rightly notes that secondments are not suitable for staff who have outgrown their current role, nor to manage poor performance. As with the Civil Service, secondment is treated as something to be initiated by the individual or business unit. In DiSSCo it seems likely that in at least some instances, secondment will be driven by the central or consortium needs of the infrastructure - a rather different model to these examples.

3.3 Examples of secondment schemes in Germany

A secondment (German: Abordnung) in the Civil Service in Germany is defined as a temporary assignment to a different agency or institution of the same or a different employer. Secondments are possible between institutions at the federal, regional, and communal (municipal) level. For civil servants (German: Beamte), secondments can last up to five years⁷. Unlike the other schemes examined here, these secondments can be in part as well as for a whole task or role – they are usually based on conducting the same or a similar role but in a new location, rather than undertaking entirely new or separate work. Under some circumstances, the civil servant can be mandated to go on secondment – usually their consent is required however the secondment will usually be at the initiative of their employer. This may have some relevance to circumstances where DiSSCo may need to ‘place’ key individuals to undertake certain work rather than offering open application to secondment schemes, although it is extremely unlikely that DiSSCo would ever be able to mandate individuals or institutions to participate in secondments. The receiving employer pays the salary and must usually continue to apply the same terms of employment.

3.4 EU staff exchange schemes

There are a variety of staff and skills exchange or visit schemes within the EU, including for example:

- Short term Scientific Missions as part of the Mobilise Cost Action⁸: These are visits of up to six months, aimed at fostering collaboration and giving access to kit or techniques that may not be available in the ‘home’ institution of participants. These are not traditional secondments given their focus on research outcomes, but do have many features in common with a more infrastructure or skills-focused secondment and could serve as a model of a funding scheme.

⁶ https://www.google.com/search?q=open+university+secondment+policy&rlz=1C1CHBD_en-GB&oq=op&aqs=chrome.0.69i59j69i57j46i199i433i465i512j69i61j69i60j69i65j69i60l2.1044j0j7&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8 (search used to access PDF 19/04/2022 – direct link inaccessible)

⁷ Civil service secondments are regulated by the *Bundesbeamtengesetz* (§ 27 Abs. 1 BBG, https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bbg_2009/_27.html) and the *Beamtenstatusgesetz* (§ 14 BeamtStG, https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/beamtstg/_14.html); for employees (German: Tarifangestellte) in the Civil Service by the *Tarifvertrag für den öffentlichen Dienst* (§ 4 Abs. 1 TVöD) <https://www.der-oeffentliche-sektor.de/infoundrat/infothek/1432> and the *Tarifvertrag für den öffentlichen Dienst der Länder* (§ 4 Abs. 1 TV-L) <https://www.tdl-online.de/tv-l/tarifvertrag.html>.

⁸ <https://www.mobilise-action.eu/2020/05/14/short-term-scientific-missions-stsms/> (page accessed 19/04/2022)

- The Erasmus+ Programme (part of the Lifelong Learning Programme)⁹: Again, this is not a traditional secondment scheme as it focuses primarily on training opportunities for students, however it also supports higher education staff to undertake professional development and for staff from the world of work to teach and train students or staff at higher education institutions, with a recognition that such opportunities may include e.g. job shadowing as well as training or teaching. The purpose of staff exchange is professional development, training and/or exchange of best practices between colleagues, learning new things, and networking.
- The Marie Curie Research & Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE)¹⁰: This had some similarities to the UK Knowledge Transfer Partnerships, requiring collaboration of three bodies across research and non-academic areas. Secondment of individuals could be funded from one to twelve months, with salary paid by the sending institution albeit funded by the scheme.

⁹ <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/programme-guide/part-b/key-action-1/mobility-project-for-higher-education-students-and-staff> (page accessed 19/04/2022)

¹⁰ <https://ris.leeds.ac.uk/eu-funding/eu-funding-opportunities/horizon-2020/marie-curie-rise/> (page accessed 19/04/2022)

04 ANALYSIS & RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Key considerations and principles for DiSSCo secondments

A key area in which DiSSCo may differ from the secondment models explored above is that DiSSCo secondments would need to benefit not only the individuals and institutions directly involved, but also the wider needs of the DiSSCo infrastructure and consortium. In other words, what would make a 'DiSSCo secondment' as opposed to any other wider exchange between our organisations would be that it delivered either skills growth / transfer considered to be needed for DiSSCo implementation; and/or concrete delivery of DiSSCo components such as technical infrastructure development.

For the most part, DiSSCo member institutions are resource-constrained and will struggle to free up staff time to spend on secondment elsewhere. This also points towards a model in which DiSSCo needs provide an additional level of incentive and coordination. It is likely that this would require a scheme that was at least partially centrally funded and administered, ensuring so far as possible that potential burdens of secondments for institutions are minimised (or evenly distributed where they cannot be avoided) and that the benefits are also well distributed and in line with overall DiSSCo requirements.

This then has some implications for policy principles and how a scheme would operate. For example, while open opportunity for such a scheme would be highly desirable, there might be circumstances where the types of skills or work needed to meet DiSSCo aims would require a more 'placed' approach to individuals with key skill sets. Similarly, while individuals might wish to make a case for opportunities, this case would need to take account of DiSSCo needs and be approved centrally in that light.

It would make sense for any DiSSCo-funded and administered secondment scheme to be made available via the DiSSCo Infrastructure, i.e. via ELViS in common with existing opportunities such as SYNTHESYS+ access. While a secondment scheme would have a different purpose and duration than SYNTHESYS+ Transnational Access, there may be elements of that scheme and of how the application process has been implemented that could be adapted to a secondment scheme.

In practice, while secondment is a useful tool to consider for DiSSCo, there are likely to be other options for delivering DiSSCo work in many cases, including distributed team working within or alongside people's existing roles. Distributed working will be examined further, with reference to one or more current pilots of how DiSSCo platforms and tools are being developed, as the next stage in this Task 3.2 of DiSSCo Prepare.

ANNEX 1 – NHM London Secondment Policy 2022

SECONDMENT AND INTERNAL RECRUITMENT POLICY

1. Policy Statement

The Museum encourages the development and progression of staff to realise their potential. One way to support the aim for everyone to thrive, is to enable opportunities for staff to undertake different work on a short-term basis to broaden their experience and develop their skills in new areas of activity. This policy supports that intention and sets out the relevant procedures involved.

2. Scope and definitions

This policy applies to all employees of the Museum, including part-time employees and those on fixed-term contracts.

The definition of a secondment is a fixed term move, either internally or externally, to a different role or to undertake work that sits outside the scope of the usual job description.

3. Policy principles

Usually, a secondment would be made available as a development opportunity or for colleagues to experience different work activities. A secondment may be created due to unusual work demands within a team, to support a project or as an agreed means to offer different work opportunities to others to support development or collaboration. A secondment may also arise in order to cover the role of a colleague who has in turn taken up a secondment of their own, away from their substantive post, such as to cover maternity leave.

Given these aims, the experience and skills expected from colleagues to take up the opportunity would usually be transferable and focused on capability. Where possible these opportunities will be opened as widely as possible with a structured process, to ensure fair appointment where interest is greater than the opportunity available. There may, however, also be cases where it is appropriate to limit the opportunity for business reasons, either due to the specialised needs of the work or to support diversity initiatives, succession planning or development aims.

When a colleague can undertake a secondment opportunity, a key consideration will be the management and delivery of their substantive/regular post. Line managers would be expected to support the secondment unless there are exceptional reasons not to, and this would be discussed with HR before any decision is made. Subject to the length of the secondment, consideration will need to be made for covering the work or if a backfill needs to be requested through the recruitment request process.

4. Related Policies

TBC

5. Roles and Responsibilities

Line Managers

Line managers are encouraged to make secondment opportunities available where possible, to support the Museum's aims for progression and development. Line managers of those applying for, or offered a secondment opportunity, should support their team member with their secondment unless there is an exceptional reason which they should discuss with HR. They should also work with HR to clarify the backfill arrangements.

HR

HR are responsible for the implementation of this policy. They will also support managers with identifying and promoting secondment opportunities where possible, along with the relevant actions outlined in the policy.

6. Policy details

This policy covers the following:

- 6.1 External secondment
- 6.2 Formal secondment programme (central or department led)
- 6.3 Internal secondment (informal: under 6 months or ongoing ad hoc input on a project)
- 6.4 Internal Recruitment that results in a formal secondment opportunity for a fixed term
- 6.5 Internal Recruitment that results in a permanent move to a fixed term post
- 6.6 Extensions to secondments and sequential secondments
- 6.7 How internal candidates will be treated in secondments and recruitment processes
- 6.8 Automatic appointments and exceptions to internal competition
- Appendix 1 – Policy Summary Table

6.1 External secondment

A formal placement with another organisation for a fixed duration. There can be several variations:

6.1.1 Embedding in a project run by, or in partnership with, another organisation, which means the colleague will be located elsewhere with the host organisation for the duration of the project. They will be line managed by the host organisation but will remain an employee of the Museum. In this case a formal agreement will confirm that their substantive role with the Museum will resume at the end of the project, and they will recommence their being located at the Museum. The employee's substantive role will be held open with the Museum for a maximum period of 18 months on this basis. Or:

6.1.2 An agreement to support the colleague to take on a new role at another organisation for a fixed duration, on the basis this appointment will further develop the aims of the Museum as well as provide professional development. There are two options to this:

- **The colleague ceases to be an employee of the Museum and takes a contract with the host organisation who becomes their new employer.** Their substantive role at the Museum will be held open for them to return for a maximum period of 18 months. Their substantive role may be back filled by fixed term cover if business needs require this. Continuity of service is maintained but reckonable service will not be, unless the organisation is a Civil Service employer and the colleague is a member of the Civil Service Pension Scheme, meaning employer and employee contributions can continue.

Note: *Continuity of service* is the ongoing total length of time from the employment start dates and this is used when considering benefits or contractual terms e.g. annual leave, redundancy calculations. *Reckonable service* is the periods of employment which are applicable for pension contributions.

- **Alternatively, the colleague can remain an employee of the Museum and all terms and conditions remain unchanged.** The Museum will invoice the host organisation for the costs related to the secondment and a formal agreement will be made to ensure clarity in terms of policies and procedures related to performance, conduct and absence.

The Museum, through the line manager or other nominated person(s), will establish keep in touch arrangements and towards the end of the secondment, will put in place a clear re-induction and re-entry process to support the colleagues return to their substantive role.

6.2 Formal secondment programme (central or department led)

This will be a centrally organised scheme, either Museum-wide or in a specific department(s), which will provide formal fixed term opportunities for colleagues to undertake different work or development activities. The details of the scheme will be made clear when advertised and will make reference to this policy as appropriate.

6.3 Internal secondment (informal: under 6 months or ongoing, ad hoc input on a project)

This will be an opportunity that has opened to invite a colleague or colleagues to be involved with a project or new, specific stand-alone activity within a team or department on an informal, fixed term basis. The individual would normally remain in their substantive post and no job title or cost code change would take place. However, there would need to be agreement from the existing line manager to release the colleague to take up the secondment work. They may move to be embedded with the team or deliver the work in their usual workspace.

Whilst there would not usually be a need for any form of competition, equality of opportunity and fair decision making should underpin the approach taken, and this may necessitate allowing for wider expressions of interest and identifying a transparent selection process. A more structured process may also be needed if the opportunity is to be offered beyond a team or department.

6.4 Internal Recruitment that results in a Formal Secondment Opportunity for a fixed term

This will be where a formal position is established on a fixed term basis for up to 18 months. This includes maternity cover vacancies to cover an established role. It will have been approved through the recruitment request process with a clear cost code, role title and job description.

Key features are:

- The opportunity will be filled through an open competition, which will usually include submission of an expression of interest or suitability statement, an interview, and any appropriate assessment.
- The approach to the recruitment and advertising will be considered and agreed with HR when the post is approved for advertising.
- Depending on the length of the secondment, the manager of the post may choose to limit the recruitment of the pool to their team or wider department if they are looking to focus development opportunities locally. Otherwise, a formal recruitment and selection process will be followed, open to all employees. If the internal pool does not generate a suitable shortlist, a manager can decide to advertise to the external market as well.
- If, after advertising, there is only one applicant the recruiting manager may choose to reduce the assessment requirements as no competition is required but they should ensure suitability and mutual understanding about the needs of the role.

- If there is a possibility that the post is to be extended or to become permanent, then this should be made clear at the advertising stage, otherwise open competition will be required at a later stage.
- The substantive post of the person taking up the seconded role will be held open for the duration of the secondment and the department will need to arrange for the work to be covered or secure a fixed term backfill. HR will support with this process.

6.5 Internal Recruitment that results in a permanent move to a Fixed Term Post

Where a post is advertised on a permanent or fixed term basis over 18 months and secured by an employee, this will be classified as recruitment rather than a secondment opportunity.

Key features are:

- A full and formal recruitment and selection process will be established and followed, open to all employees across the Museum. If the internal pool does not generate a suitable shortlist, a manager can decide to advertise to the external market as well.
- Colleagues who secure a new permanent or fixed term role over 18 months in duration will not automatically have their substantive role available to them once the fixed term role ends.
- The substantive post of the person taking up the new role will not automatically be held open for the duration of the secondment and the department will backfill the post through the NHM's standard recruitment process.

6.6 Extensions to Secondments

Where a formal secondment is extended, or an employee secures sequential secondments comprising different roles, the employee's substantive post will be preserved up to 18 months. After this time, subsequent opportunities (regardless of their length/duration) will fall under the criteria of section 6.5 of this policy, subject to a conversation with the substantive post department.

Where this is the case, the employee will be appointed to a fixed term post rather than a secondment, and their employment with NHM will end of the proposed end date. It is important for the seconded manager to discuss any plans to extend with HR and the line manager of the employee's substantive post. This will ensure open communication and that the approach taken aligns with the principles of this policy and meets business need.

6.7 How internal candidates will be treated in secondment and recruitment processes

Interviewing for secondments and internal candidates in recruitment campaigns

- The Museum recognises that the process of applying for a new opportunity can be an important development activity.
- If an employee is not successful at either the application stage or selection process for a secondment opportunity, they will always be offered feedback from the recruiting manager and can discuss areas for development with their line manager.
- If an interview process is established for an informal secondment opportunity, then usually all interested colleagues who meet the essential criteria would be interviewed.
- Subject to numbers of applications, internal candidates who meet the person specification in their application for an internal recruitment opportunity (sections 6.4 and 6.5), will be invited to interview and any related assessment activity.
- Training on interview skills and CV preparation are part of the core offer available to colleagues as part of their ongoing development and to support progression.

Line managers input on secondments and internal candidates for recruitment

- Individuals wishing to take up an informal secondment opportunity will need to discuss and agree this with their line manager first. The secondment forms part of ongoing development and the line manager will also need to ensure the work the colleague leaves behind can be covered.
- For an internal recruitment process under sections 6.4 and 6.5 of this policy, an internal candidate is under no obligation to tell their current line manager they are applying for an internal opportunity but open conversation on career aspirations and development opportunities is encouraged and should be supported. Line managers should be supportive where they are aware of an application being made.
- The recruiting manager may talk to the current manager about the candidate's suitability for the role after the interview process and this can be considered in any decision-making, so engagement in the role may be contingent on the recommendations of the current manager as a form of internal reference.
- Should the current manager not recommend the candidate, they must outline their reasons fully to their team member and ensure developmental points are identified and the matter built into the next appraisal discussion.

6.8 Automatic appointments and exceptions to internal competition

Fixed term to permanent

If a fixed term contract was advertised with a disclaimer that there is a possibility it could be made permanent, then there will be no further requirement to advertise and the person in the role can be made permanent.

Evolution of existing roles

There may be times when business needs require an existing role to operate differently. A process will be followed for updating the job description to reflect the new requirements of the role and a job evaluation undertaken. Where the role moves into a higher job family it may represent a promotion opportunity for the current role holder. If they can demonstrate capability for that role then it may be appropriate for them to automatically take on the new, evolved, higher level version of their role. This process is set out in the Museum Pay Management Guidelines.

This also applies where an employee is appointed in a fixed term role and business need identifies that we need to make the role permanent and as a result, an automatic appointment may be made without the need for any further recruitment process. This action may be appropriate to avoid a redundancy situation or where the permanent role effectively replaces the fixed term position, and it would therefore not be appropriate to open the opportunity up to a wider recruitment process, given that the post-holder can fulfil the duties of the post.

Matching opportunities

There may be times when it is appropriate for an individual to be matched to a vacant internal opportunity without a competition process. This could be where there has been a restructure and an individual faces risk of redundancy.

Another situation where a placement may be made without competition is where the position could provide a suitable alternative role for somebody who is unable to fulfil their current role due to disability and where movement into this role could be deemed a reasonable adjustment under the Equality Act 2010.

Appendix 1 – Policy Summary Table

	6.1 External Secondment	6.2 Formal Secondment Programme	6.3 Internal Secondment <i>(informal, <6 months or ongoing input to project or work)</i>	6.4 Internal Recruitment: Secondment <i>(formal, up to 18 months)</i>	6.5 Internal Recruitment: Perm or Fixed Term <i>(formal, > 18 months)</i>
Requisition Process	Formal Agreement with host organisation, SCF logged for employee change	Business case will be drawn up and approved	None – need arises within team and manager owns process	NHM Recruitment Request process, with sign off by Resourcing Panel	NHM Recruitment Request process, with sign off by Resourcing Panel
Selection / Assessment Process	Led by host organisation	Formal assessment process likely to be established to ensure fair selection and appointment	Not mandatory but may be required where interest is greater than the opportunity available. Led by manager (no HR involvement)	Manager may choose to limit the recruitment pool to their team or wider department, or a wider process may be established. Otherwise, full recruitment and selection process open to all employees. If the internal pool does not generate a suitable shortlist, a manager can decide to advertise to the external market as well.	A full recruitment and selection process open to all employees. If the internal pool does not generate a suitable shortlist, a manager can decide to advertise to the external market as well.
Status of Substantive Post	Preserved up to maximum period of 18 months	Dependent on details of the programme, in line with principles of this policy	Preserved/no change (secondment is for 6 months or less)	Preserved for full duration of secondment	Not preserved, employee will move to fixed term employment or the new permanent role
Documents	JD, Formal agreement and either keep NHM contract & work is invoiced to host org, or contract issued by host org	Recruitment Requests, JDs, selection & assessment docs and Staff Change Forms for successful employees	None - job title and project/cost codes remain the same	Recruitment Request, JD, selection & assessment docs and Staff Change form for successful employee	Recruitment Request, JD, selection & assessment docs and Staff Change form for successful employee
Potential to backfill?	Yes, determined case by case	Yes, depending on the details of the programme	No	Yes, depending on outputs of substantive post	Yes

